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CUTLER - Coastal Urban developmentT through the Lenses of Resiliency

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Short report on

**Methodology for modelling
decision-making processes in
public administrations**

**Authors: Holger Haberstock, Laszlo Kovats –
EUROSOC#DIGITAL gGmbH**

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Introduction

The key objective of the CUTLER platform is to shift the existing paradigm of policy making, which is largely based on intuition, towards an evidence-driven approach enabled by big data. However, the prerequisite for any evidence-based, data driven policy making is to provide policy planners and decision-makers with exactly the required data at exactly the right state of the policy formulation process. In the CUTLER context this means to introduce big data applications into the standard steps of policy formulation in order to complement traditional ways of decision-making. This makes at least slight adjustments in the traditional working procedures necessary. The challenge lies in the fact that the working procedures of public administrations are relatively resistant to change and do not adapt easily to technology induced modifications.

The objective of the methodology presented here is to provide business process models (BPMs) that bridge the big data technology of the CUTLER system with the policy development routines in the pilot administrations. A key requirement of these models is to provide a smooth transition from how administrative staff usually works to slightly adapted workflows with integrated big data applications that are accepted by the actors within the administrations.

This updated short report describes briefly the applied methodology to secure this outcome. It shows the process from creating as-is business process models of the standard mid-term to long-term decision-making procedures in the pilot administrations to the identification of the suitable entry points for big data applications down to detailed working procedures on an operational level defining all human and technical process flows and their interaction. It further reports about the continuous re-iteration of operational business process models of the -now five- CUTLER pilot cases to come up with a workable CUTLER process model that can be tested and applied in real-world circumstances.

The results are business process models that guide policy makers through a new data-driven evidence-based policy formulation process that fits to the day-to-day working routines in the administrations.

A second aspect of our methodology is to safeguard that the specific functionalities and features of the big data applications which will be developed match the needs and requirements of the administrative staff. This is done by following strictly user centered methods to elicit and present end-user requirements borrowed from AGILE software development methodologies.

The detailed explanations of the topics presented here can be found in the following public CUTLER deliverables:

- D7.1 “*The Baseline Business Process Model for CUTLER*”¹
- D7.2 “*The CUTLER Business Process Model – Intermediate Results*”²
- D7.3 “*Applied CUTLER Business Process Model*”³
- D7.4 “*Optimized CUTLER BPM based on the evaluation feedback from the city pilots*”⁴

¹ <https://www.cutler-h2020.eu/download/544>

² <https://www.cutler-h2020.eu/download/547>

³ <https://www.cutler-h2020.eu/download/550>

⁴ <https://www.cutler-h2020.eu/download/1196>

Process Modelling

Business Process Modeling or Business Process Management (BPM) respectively is a systematic attempt to research processes, the involved actors, their tasks and interrelations. The suitable tool we use to capture the results of this research and to model these processes is Business Process Modelling and Notation 2.0 (BPMN 2.0). BPMN 2.0 provides a standardized graphical notation format for capturing business processes that is intuitive to business users, yet also able to represent complex process semantics. It is therefore understandable by process analysts, administrative staff as well as software developers alike. Since BPMN 2.0 can easily be transferred into machine readable XML expressions, it can be used to execute processes by running them in a business process engine. Since 2005, the Object Management Group (OMG) has been responsible for the notation and its further development. The BPMN has been ISO standard since September 2013.

Communication is Key

Business Process Management is not simply about capturing processes graphically. It rather is an activity on its own and much more than a final product (the process models). It is an intensive and continuous communication process between us as process analysts, the administrative staff in the pilot cases and the technical and analytical work packages, involving a lot of debate, negotiation and agreement between those various actors with their different viewpoints and interests.

The basis for creating every process model (baseline, strategic and operational) was a vast document research reaching from official documents like laws, regulations, organisational charts and specific legislation up to informal sources like presentations and papers. From such written source material, we derive a first understanding of the administrative working procedures. Nevertheless, the main and most important source of information are one on one interviews and workshops. From the insights gained there we extracted the relevant tasks which the pilot cases have to perform and brought them into a first logical process flow which lead to first drafts of process models. These first drafts serve as basis for discussion and negotiation and are changing constantly while alterations are incorporated, and misunderstandings eliminated. This was followed by numerous workshops and focus groups consisting of the pilot-case partners, software developers and process modellers to come up with a workable CUTLER process model that can be tested and applied in real-world circumstances. Every workshop and focus group contributed to refining the requirements for the CUTLER platform and increasing the mutual understanding, which was necessary to develop the right software widgets for the right purposes.

Research Design and Research Process

From general to specific: Three different kinds of process models

The challenge we are facing is to capture and model policy formulation processes in the pilot administrations that range from large and long-term decision making procedures involving different administrative units and governmental bodies up to small day-to-day workflows of policy planning activities from administrative staff that will potentially be using the CUTLER platform.

To capture all these different processes as well as their interrelations and hierarchical dependencies we structured them according to three different types of process models which we call Baseline BPMs, Strategic CUTLER BPMs and Operational CUTLER BPMs (see Fig. 1)

Figure 1: The relationship of Baseline, Strategic and Operational Process Models

Baseline Process Models

Baseline BPMs depict the general institutional arrangements of the pilot cases administrations in their entirety but on a general level. Roughly speaking the baseline processes describe how information is gathered among different administrative departments, how policy papers are created and how policy options are derived on which a decision-making body on municipal level (e.g. a City Council) can vote on. These Baseline Process Models present the institutional playing field where all administrative and political action takes place and they serve as an orientation framework to which all further processes are aligned to. Four Baseline Process Models have been produced in the CUTLER project – one for each pilot case. Figure 2 presents an excerpt from the Baseline Process Model of the Antalya pilot case.

Figure 2: Excerpt from Baseline Process Model of Antalya

Strategic Process Models

Strategic Process Models are created according to the pilot cases’ policy objectives. Antalya wishes to improve the touristic capabilities of the area surrounding Düden Brook Waterfalls to increase the visitor numbers. Antwerp wants to monitor and evaluate its Strategic Urban Waterplan and to plan, implement and monitor a Garden Street as a specific flood prevention measure. Cork County will facilitate the touristic exploitation of Camden Fort Meagher, also to increase visitor numbers and Thessaloniki aims to plan, implement, monitor and evaluate the use of a new Controlled Parking System.⁵

Strategic Process Models show a concise and complete picture of the processes that that the municipalities have to perform to reach those goals. They describe on a medium abstraction level what tasks and activities must be carried in the correct logical and sequential order. In these process models the high-level tasks of the baseline models are more specified. Furthermore, they already depict adequate entry points for the CUTLER big data applications in the decision-making and planning procedures. Similar to the Baseline Process Models, the Strategic Process models serve as the orientation framework for Operational Process Models. We developed one strategic model for the pilot cases of Antwerp, Cork and Thessaloniki and two models for the pilot case of Antalya. Figure 3 shows one of the Antalya models.

Figure 3: Strategic Process Model for Antalya

Operational Process Models

Since Strategic Process Models describe the pilot cases workflows as compact, comprehensive and easy to understand as possible, they lack details. To capture the complex and detailed workflows and sub-processes that are hidden beneath and in between the high-level tasks of the strategic models, we create Operational Process Models. Operational Process Models depict the detailed working procedures on an operational level defining all human and technical process flows and their interaction. These models reveal how the work in the pilot administrations is actually performed on a

⁵ For a description of the pilots please refer to deliverable D9.1 “Report on pilot preparations and pilot execution plan”, <https://www.cutler-h2020.eu/download/559>

day to day basis. These models are the basis for creating customized versions of the platform that are used to execute the city pilots and evaluate the impact of the designed policies. Since Operational Process Models depict every process participant from humans up to sensors and software services as well as all the tasks they perform, Operational Process Models can be implemented by a workflow or business process engine. For each pilot case several Operational Process Models have to be created to capture the multitude of small day-to-day workflows necessary to implement their policy objectives. Figure 4 presents an Operational Process Model again from the pilot case of Antalya.

Figure 4: Operational Process Model from Antalya

Creating a first vision of the platform functionalities

A second important element of our methodology besides modelling the decision-making processes is to make sure that the functionalities of the big data applications match to the needs, expectations and requirements of the administrative staff. This task is basically about creating a vision of the CUTLER platform functionalities before any technical implementation is done. Our methodology for this work is to gather end-user requirements in the form of so-called user stories, create story maps and create wireframes.

User Stories

A Use Story is a short one sentence description of a software feature from the viewpoint of a user that express

- the form of user,
- what he wants to do with the feature and
- what he wants to use it for.

The generic form of a user story reads as:

- As a < form of user>, I want <to do smth.>, so that <some benefit>

which can also be complemented by further details about the software feature called acceptance criteria. An example of a complete user story from the pilot case of Cork can be seen in Figure 5.

As a (User Role)... Platform User

I want (do something)... to select, and view, datasets as individual layers, from the data layer inventory/ side panel

So that (some benefit)... I can view specific layers of data on the base map, which will help with decision making.

Acceptance Criteria

- Allow data layers to be selected/unselected
- If data layer is selected, display information/ visualise information on the base map
- Select and display more than one data layer simultaneously must be possible
- Selecting main layer selects all pertaining sub-layers
- Deselect all data-layers option
- Deselect all sub-layers option
- Select a sub-layer within a data layer to be displayed (only possible if main data layer selected)

Figure 5: User Story from the Cork pilot case

Story Maps

After more than 180 User Stories have been created in an extensive communication process with the pilot cases, we created large story maps for each pilot case. Each story map creates an overview of all software features as expressed in the user stories by grouping similar features, bringing features in a logical sequence and matching sub-features to their parent features. An excerpt from the story map of the Cork pilot can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Excerpt of a story map of the Cork pilot case.

Wireframes

The next step in our methodology after creating story maps is generating wireframes based on the user stories. Wireframes are blueprints usually of a single user interface of a website or in an application. The idea is to give an impression of the basic operation logic. Insofar wireframes are about general ideas, not exact details. Wireframing a software application is another method to elicit communication amongst all stakeholders and find the common ground before any actual technical implementation is done. They can serve as blueprints for the user interfaces that will be developed. Figure 7 shows one of the wireframes we created, and a Figure 8 shows a screenshot of the actual user interface that has been developed. As one can see although the layout and configuration are a bit different all functionalities are there.

Figure 7: Wireframe of a user interface for the pilot case of Thessaloniki

Figure 8: Actual user interface for the pilot case of Thessaloniki

Evaluating, iterating, and improving the operational BPMs, the platform and its functionalities

After having created first operational BPMs and elicited the end-user requirements we improved the operational models further in an iterative manner with the use-case partners and their technical partners. In order to do so we organised a number of focus-group meetings to go through the details of the then close to final business process models and clarify their content. Due to the fact that the business process models contain a lot of information, it can be difficult to keep the overview of all their details. Therefore, all the tasks of the presented processes were accompanied by explanatory documents that are detailing

- The objectives of the tasks and gateways,
- The basic functionalities that are demanded either by the use-case partners or the IAMER concept,
- References to the software widgets that are developed in order to implement the functionalities.

The results of the focus groups were recorded, new versions of the business process models created and the appropriated changes were made in the accompanying documents. All these results were accessible all the time by all partners. This was repeated until all involved project partners agreed that the result is satisfying and possible to implement. When the operational BPMs are implemented in the CAMUNDA process engine, they steer the platform insofar that they provide the single end-user with the appropriate information (dashboards) and the matching decision situation (decision gateways) in his decision-making process.

Figure 9: Operational BPM for Pricing Policy in Düden Waterfall

One key difference of the final operational process models to the versions before is that they do not depict non-human workflows (e.g. sensors or software devices), but only concentrate on human workflows. The reason for that is that it turned out to be more suitable for the project's needs to let the process engine only steer the human user interfaces and make them fit to the pilot cases' administrative workflows while letting sensors and software be orchestrated by Kafka and Kibana.

Deriving a generic BPM

Another output of our work was the development of a a generic CUTLER BPM that is derived from the requirements of the CUTLER logic. The CUTLER logic is, in turn, based on the propositions of the IAMER concept. We provided an explanation on how the IAMER elements are translated into an organisational workflow in a policy-making context. Therewith, the generic BPM is formulating an exemplary abstract workflow that is showing interested new users how the decision-support system CUTLER is working and which added value it provides. The generic CUTLER BPM can serve as a conceptual baseline for the business process models of any new administration who wants to use the platform. It defines an abstract decision-making process that is incorporating all the propositions of the IAMER concept. Therefore, it gives important

indications about which tasks should be performed by the users of the CUTLER platform and which functionalities and software widgets should be provided.

Figure 10: The generic CUTLER BPM

Preparing public administrations for the utilization of the CUTLER platform and including the public in the policy development process

Decision-support systems are not ordinary products that can be purchased and used right away. They have to be adapted to the customer's decision-making context that should be supported. At the same time any new administration who wants to use a data-based decision-support system like the CUTLER platform has to incorporate quantitative thinking in order to reach meaningful conclusions from a set of quantitative analyses. We described a process of a quantitative conceptual preparation of how administrations should analyze any policy they want to use the platform for. This process ranges from clarifying and defining all concepts to the definition of independent, dependent, and intervening variables up to defining hypothesis and theoretical relations. This exercise of thinking in variables, numbers and data necessarily has to take place before using a data-based decision-support system. In order to support administrations in this exercise, we developed a structured data driven scenario planning methodology for creating policy options which at the same time can be used in public participation formats. This methodology is based on methods from system thinking which are ideal to identify causal relationships between variables and feedback mechanisms and help in formulating hypotheses.

Conclusion

This report shortly summarized our work and our methodology first in modelling the decision-making procedures in the pilot cases and making sure that the slightly altered policy formulation processes include the CUTLER functionalities and are accepted by the administrative staff in the pilot administrations. Secondly, we presented our methodology to safeguard that the specific functionalities and features of the big data applications which will be developed match the needs and requirements of the administrative staff. Third, we derived a generic CUTLER BPM that can serve as an abstract blueprint for the BPMs of any new public administrations and forth, we lined out a structured data-driven scenario planning methodology to incorporate quantitative thinking in public administrations and include the public and other stakeholders in the policy formulation process.

At the core of all our work lies the deep conviction that is a strictly user centered approach accompanied by continuous and intensive communication processes involving a lot of debate, negotiation and agreement over the course of several month is necessary to reach meaningful results that provide a real service to administrations. This proves highly effective in creating a common ground and a shared understanding among all stakeholders involved.